

Paper 8

Impact of Shopping Malls on Small Retail Outlets: A Case Study Of Mangaluru City

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Abstract

Indian economy has transformed from an extensive controlled economy to a liberal market driven economy. High-income opportunities, changing attitude towards saving, international exposure and necessities of lifestyle are the key drivers for fast evolving Indian consumer behavior (KSA Technopark, 2006). Indian retail industry is witnessing a paradigm shift as the sector is getting organized and consumers are seeking a one-stop shopping place with convenience and entertainment. Professionally managed and separately owned retail organizations are the face of today's retail sector. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the effect of malls on retail outlets in the Mangaluru city. This study is limited to Mangaluru. The results from the sample respondents revealed that there has been impact of malls on the retail outlets.

Keywords: Retail business, sales, profit, malls.

Introduction:

The Indian Retail sector has come off age and has gone through major transformation over the last decade with a noticeable shift towards organised retailing. The retail market is expected to double to \$1 trillion by 2020 from \$600 billion in 2015 driven by income growth, urbanization and attitudinal. While the overall retail market will grow at 12% per annum, modern trade will grow twice as fast at 20% per annum, and traditional trade at 10% . The India Retail Industry is the largest among all the industries, accounting for over 10 per cent of the country's GDP and around 8 per cent of the employment. The Retail Industry in India has come forth as one of the most dynamic and fast paced industries with several players entering the market. But all of them have not yet tasted success because of the heavy initial investments that are required to break even with other companies and compete with them. The India Retail Industry is gradually inching its way towards becoming the next boom industry. The total concept and idea of shopping has undergone an attention drawing change in terms of format and consumer buying behaviour, ushering in a revolution in shopping in India. Modern retailing has entered into the Retail market in India as is observed in the form of bustling shopping centres, multi-storied malls and the huge complexes that offer shopping, entertainment and food all under one

roof. A large young working population with median age of 24 years, nuclear families in urban areas, along with increasing workingwomen population and emerging opportunities in the services sector are going to be the key factors in the growth of the organized Retail sector in India. The growth pattern in organized retailing and in the consumption made by the Indian population will follow a rising graph helping the newer businessmen to enter the India Retail Industry. Indian economy is dominated by agriculture sector on employment.

Objectives of the Study:

The study was conducted with the following research objectives:

- To identify the impact of malls on retail outlets.
- To study the changes in sales and profit of retail outlets because of the establishment of malls.
- To study the variations in the size of workers and customers in the retail outlets.

Research Methodology:

This study was conducted in Mangaluru City. Primary data was collected by distributing the questionnaire (Google form) and sample size for the study is fifty.

Literature review:

The review of literature shows that the emergence of shopping malls has severely influenced operations of small shopkeepers and other unorganized business outlets. The sales figures and operating profits have been shown to be badly experiencing a receding behaviour. A study on the “impact of malls on small shops and hawkers in Mumbai” (Kalhan, 2007) unambiguously indicated that there has been a severe impact of malls on the unorganised retail shops operating in the vicinity of malls. The study further stated that Mega Malls are making deep inroads in the sales of retailers operating in the unorganised retail sector. A study on the “Impact of shopping malls on the unorganized retail sector – a case study of Mangalore region” stated that the malls interestingly have no severe impact on the employment scenario. However, the study further revealed that Malls have severely impacted the Turnover and Operating profits of the sample shops. Besides, there is also an adverse impact on the customers of sample shops. A survey based study of small unorganised retailers operating in close proximity to Food World and Subhiksha (CII-KSA Technologies) in Chennai showed that none of them had to close their operations with the advent of these big organised retail formats. The study observed that there was a little impact on the sales and inventory on the selected respondents in the initial period of time; however, it changed gradually.

Sinha (2004) stated that in India, the major drivers for a grocery and FMCG stores seem to be nearness to place of residence and the comfort level that the respondent has in dealing with the store owner measured in terms of personal relationship with the shopkeeper. There are the organized retailers who are making a foray into the grocery market at a rapid rate and posing a threat to the livelihood of kirana shop owners; and on the other, there is the highly price sensitive consumer forcing market players to operate on thin margins. Marguerite Moore (2008) Study provides understanding of the manner in which consumers perceive and act upon price, beyond low-price and value, in the discount sector. The results suggest that popular

wisdom regarding price and the US discount shopper is oversimplified, which may portend even greater opportunity for discounters and threat to their intra-type competitors. Seung (2008) research analyze the factors that influence small-town consumers' satisfaction with local independent retailers and the subsequent relationships of consumer satisfaction to in-shopping, community attachment, and support of local independent retailers. Most strategies performed by small-town independent retailers did not meet their local consumers' expectations. Specially, merchandise assortment and availability, such as offering a unique and large selection of products, showed the largest discrepancy between respondents' expectations and retailers' performance, indicating that independent retailers are not meeting their consumers' needs in these areas.

Singh (2002) research indicates that grocery shoppers consider quality to be most important, followed by price, locality, range of products and parking. Similarly, Seiders (2000) stated that those primary shoppers of food and FMCG items prefer low price and assortment more often as the reason for store choice; traditional supermarket primary shoppers were less willing to trade off location convenience or, in some cases, quality and assortment. According to Teller (2006) large stores (associated with the great amounts of goods, special offers and a lot of walking and searching) from small stores (associated with personal attention, accessibility, nearness, high prices) but as far as consumer choice is concerned consumers are not able to perceive an important difference between home delivery and traditional grocery shopping . According to Park (1988) Indian shoppers generally use the modern format for their weekly and monthly shopping needs and use traditional stores for “top-up” shopping. An important factor that has an impact on grocery shopping behavior is unplanned buying,

Data Analysis, interpretation and findings:

This study is focused on the impact of malls on retail outlets. Under this study effort is put to analyze the impact of malls on profit, sales and number of workers and customers. Collected data were presented in tabular form.

Demographic profile of the respondents:

VARIABLE		Frequency	Percentage
Total no. of Respondents		50	100
Type of ownership	Sole trading	24	48
	Partnership	26	52
	Others	0	0
Life of the business:	1-10 years	38	76
	11-20 years	12	24
	Above 21 years	0	0
No. of workers	Less than 10	42	84
	10-20	8	16
	21-30	0	0
	Above 30	0	0

Store ownership	Owned	16	32
	Leased	30	60
	Rented	4	8
Retail segment	General stores/ bakery/ gift shops	16	32
	apparel and textiles	14	28
	footwear	14	28
	medical stores	6	12
Location of store	Market area	16	32
	City area	34	68
	sub-urban area	0	0
	rural area	0	0
No. of competitors	1-5	48	96
	6-10	2	4
	more than 10	0	0
Business effected by malls culture	Yes	44	88
	No	6	12

From the table it is clear that 52% of the retail outlets are partnership firms and remaining 48% are sole traders. 76% of the respondents running their business from last 10 years and 24% of them falls under 11-20 years. Out of 50 retailers 42 shops are having less than 10 workers and 8 shops are having workers between 10-20. 60% of the shops running their business in leased outlet, 32% of them are using their own property only 8% of retailers running their business in rented outlet. 32% of outlets belongs to general stores, 28% of outlets from apparel and footwear business. Only 12% falls under medical stores. 68% of respondents running their business in city area and remaining 32% are running in market area. Around 96% Respondents opine that they have less competition. 88% of respondents agree that malls effects their business whereas 12% of respondents opine that their business is not affected.

Table showing impact of malls on retail outlets:

Elements	Increased	%	Decreased	%	No change	%
On sales	18	41	26	59	-	-
On profit	20	45	24	55	-	-
On no. of customers	18	41	26	59	-	-
On no. of workers	4	9	40	91	-	-

From the above table it is clear that 59% of respondents feel that their sales are affected by malls. 55% of them opine that even profit is decreased this is because there is a direct relationship between sale and profit. In the size of Number of workers and customers there is

drastic impact. Because of the establishment of malls the profitability of retailers decreased and operating cost increased so they are not afford to have more number of workers. The main reason for shift in customer preferences from retail shops to malls are availability of branded products, attractive offers, customer service, grievance cell, parking space, increase in the standard of livings availability of variety products.

Conclusion:

If the number of malls and retail chains multiply, the sales impact on small shops is likely to be intensified and earnings will keep falling till all these micro accumulators become micro-subsistence seekers. FDI in retail and the growth of large corporate retail trade will slowly erode the informal petty accumulators and increase the masses of the informal proletariat. From the study it is clear that establishment of malls in Mangaluru drastically affected sales, profit, number of workers and customers of retail outlets. There is a need to develop strategies to compete with the malls in order to sustain in the future.

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